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DE-RISK Project

D6.3: Market Actors Community

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D	Deliverable
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
ER	Exploitable Result
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LFM	Local Flexibility Market
M	Month
T	Task
RES	Renewable Energy System
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report contains the deliverable **D6.3: Market Actors Community** of the Horizon Europe project DE-RISK — *DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems* (funded under Grant Agreement No. 101075515), showing the results obtained from task *T6.3: Project market actors, stakeholder dissemination and exploitation events*. All the partners of the project participate in this task.

This deliverable provides an overview of the DE-RISK Market Actors Community, that is, the project's targeted stakeholders database.

This deliverable, D6.3, presents the progress and development of the DE-RISK Market Actors Community, a key component of the DE-RISK project. DE-RISK aims to facilitate the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs) to support the large-scale deployment of Renewable Energy Systems (RES). The database consists of a spreadsheet that is used to register and cluster the targeted stakeholders, who will receive the DE-RISK project's newsletters as well as exploitation-oriented communication & dissemination materials, and will be invited to the project's workshops and events.

The main objective of the DE-RISK Market Actors Community is to establish a comprehensive stakeholder network to disseminate the DE-RISK project's results, gather valuable feedback, and contribute to the wider market engagement needed for the project's long-term impact and success. The Market Actors Community has been built by aggregating the top contacts from Consortium partners' networks, focusing on stakeholders who can influence the market adoption of LFMs. As of March 2025, DE-RISK has achieved the milestone of +100 contacts in the Market Actors Community. The stakeholders in the database, which have signed a *Letter of Interest and Support* for DE-RISK, represent a balanced mix of private industry, research institutions, non-profit organisations, and public entities, reflecting the broad reach and inclusivity of the project's engagement strategy.

Key benefits of engaging with these stakeholders include knowledge exchange, first-mover opportunities for adopting LFMs, and participation in shaping future market standards. The Market Actors Community will play a pivotal role in amplifying DE-RISK's impact through tailored communication and dissemination efforts. The engagement and feedback from this community will be critical in shaping DE-RISK's post-project exploitation strategies, ensuring that the project's results meet market needs and drive the adoption of LFMs to achieve the goal of unlocking flexibility by 2030.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Overview of the DE-RISK project

DE-RISK, whose acronym stands for “*DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems*” is a project funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement n° 101075515.

DE-RISK aims to support the market uptake of Renewable Energy Systems (RES) by fostering the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs) and unlocking up to 100 GW of flexibility in 2030 which will allow a safe and reliable integration of RES in the grid. DE-RISK will achieve this ambitious objective by minimising the investments and implementation risk through an innovative consumer behaviour change journey that will increase end-users’ trust and willingness to participate in the LFMs.

1.2. Description of the deliverable content, objectives and purpose

This report corresponds to the deliverable **D6.3: Market Actors Community**. Its aim is to provide an overview of the DE-RISK Market Actors Community (stakeholder database) as of 31st March 2025. The database serves the following general purposes:

1. To provide a common repository of the DE-RISK project’s key stakeholder contacts to receive dissemination and communication materials.
2. To enable clustering and analysis of the database so that the project’s exploitation space can be defined and gaps can be filled; and the partners are aware of who is targeted to receive the project’s information and potential competitiveness concerns can be avoided.
3. To provide a tool to help quantify the project’s impact.

The creation of the DE-RISK Market Actors Community began by aggregating the top contacts from the Consortium partners’ networks, and it will keep evolving and growing along the lifespan of the project. The current state of the Market Actors Community has been analysed in order to identify and cluster the different types of stakeholders already available.

It is important to note that the database of the DE-RISK stakeholder community is confidential, and that each partner remains the owner of its contacts. Partners have authorization to communicate with their own stakeholders and the C&D Manager, will only contact directly (on behalf of the project) those stakeholders who have granted their consent to be informed about the DE-RISK project activities and results, in compliance with the EU’s regulation on data protection and privacy (GDPR).

2. DE-RISK Market Actors Community

2.1. Expected benefits from the stakeholders' engagement

As outlined in *D6.1: Communication & Dissemination Plan*, the DE-RISK project's efforts to engage stakeholders bring benefits to both parties (the Consortium and the stakeholders).

DE-RISK gains from the stakeholders' engagement mainly on:

- Dissemination and networking.
- First/early adopters and advocates.
- Expectations and feedback.
- Knowledge exchange.
- Alignment with market and industry needs.
- Potential markets.

Stakeholders, in turn, gain from being part of the DE-RISK community:

- Access to project public outcomes and results.
- Research outputs.
- New research opportunities.
- Networking.
- Publicity.
- Knowledge exchange.
- Potential new partners for marketing products and services.

Table 1 clearly identifies the benefits from engaging each particular stakeholder group:

Table 1: Benefits from the stakeholders' engagement.

Target audiences / Stakeholder groups	Benefits
General public & Media	Inform, educate and raise awareness about DE-RISK's technology, activities and results, their relevance for the energy transition, and their social and environmental benefits.
Academia & Scientific community	Ensure knowledge transfer through targeted dissemination and synergic collaboration in research activities for future system optimization.
Industry	Increase awareness and stakeholder engagement to evaluate the potential future applicabilities of DE-RISK technologies and results.

Target audiences / Stakeholder groups	Benefits
	Establish mutually-beneficial interaction to accelerate market uptake.
Sector associations	Obtain access to various platforms, extending the DE-RISK project's impact at EU level. Collect and analyse insights and feedback.
Service providers / ESCOs	Evaluate potential business models and simulate applicability of the DE-RISK technological solution in real scenarios.
Policy-makers & Standardisation bodies	Inform and engage decision-makers to influence policy-making, analyse and contribute to standardisation to help reduce any existing or future barrier that could affect the project's impact and market uptake.
Similar R&I projects	Stay abreast of research efforts worldwide. Ensure knowledge transfer. Establish mutually-beneficial interaction. Collect relevant insights and feedback.

2.2. Market Actors Community Approach

DESIGN: First, the desired fields of entry were identified and selected. In doing so, the intent was to capture necessary information but not to include too many filters such that the database became cumbersome or that data finding became a barrier to including good contacts. The fields included in the DE-RISK DE-RISK Market Actors Community database are the following:

Table 2: Fields in the DE-RISK DE-RISK Market Actors Community.

Field	Explanation / Rationale
#	For count.
Referred by	Partner referring the contact.
Contact person	Name and last name of the contact person.
Position	Position of the contact person.
Organisation	Organisation represented by the contact person.
Stakeholder type	Organisation type for clustering.
Country	Country where the contact person is based, for clustering and analysis of the geographical coverage.
Email address	Email address of the contact person for receipt of communication & dissemination materials.
Webpage	Webpage of the organisation.
Status	A field reserved to show if a stakeholder is "proposed" or "confirmed".
Comments	A field to explain the rationale for inclusion, enabling other partners to understand why any particular stakeholder was important / targeted by the referring partner.

POPULATION, AGGREGATION AND APPROVAL: The database spreadsheet was circulated to each of the partners for their input, aggregating the top 5-10 exploitation-related contacts of the partners. As the database was circulated and iterated, the Consortium partners had the opportunity to revise and approve the entrants into the database (e.g., selected contacts being removed for competitiveness concerns from the industrial partners).

CLUSTERING & ANALYTICS: Once the database was populated, the entrants were organised and clustered by the following categories:

- **Count** – total number of members in the DE-RISK Market Actors Community.
- **Clustering by organisation type (detailed)**
 - LE: Large Enterprises.
 - SME: Small and Medium-sized Enterprises.
 - RTO: Research & Technology Organizations.
 - UNI: Universities or high-level education institutions.
 - GOV: Governmental institutions.
 - NPO: Non-Profit Organisations.
 - Media: Various media platforms.
- **Clustering by organisation type (aggregated)**
 - Industry
 - Research
 - Other
- **Clustering by country**

The above phases of the approach (i.e., database design, initial population and initial analytics) have been completed and have resulted in this report. Next, as the DE-RISK project continues, the following phases will take place:

IMPLEMENTATION AND USE: With the availability of this report, the database can be used:

- To facilitate a widespread release of the DE-RISK project's C&D materials.
- To provide information related to the project's exploitation space across various presentations, the project's website and other C&D literature.

REDESIGN AND UPDATING: Beginning with the next project meeting, and systematically moving forward, the DE-RISK Market Actors Community can be used by the Consortium as a tool to take decisions related to the shaping and execution of the *IPR & Exploitation Plan*. Database updates will happen in a natural way as new contacts are made by the project's partners, and a systematic call for updates and recalculation of the database indicators will be conducted for each periodic report.

2.3. Results and analytics

Currently (as of March 2025), the DE-RISK Market Actors Community counts **225 members** in its database: **101 stakeholders which have signed a *Letter of Interest and Support*** for the DE-RISK project; and 124 additional stakeholders subscribed to the DE-RISK newsletter. Only the 101 engaged stakeholders that have signed a *Letter of Interest and Support*, representing different organisations in 13 countries, have been analysed in this report. Although the personal data of the stakeholders (i.e., name, last name, email address, etc.) cannot be shared in this deliverable for GDPR compliance, the names of the organisations that have been engaged are shown below in *Table 3*.

The engaged stakeholders will receive information about the DE-RISK project (i.e., updates, new developments and future activities, etc.) via email, through the project's newsletter, as well as exploitation-oriented communication & dissemination materials. They might also be asked for their feedback on some of the project's results according to their experience. For instance, key stakeholders will be invited to participate in the DE-RISK workshops.

Table 3: DE-RISK Market Actors Community (Stakeholder Database).

#	Organisation	Position	Type	Country	Website
1	European University of Tirana	Deputy Administrator	Higher or secondary education establishment	Albania	https://uet.edu.al
2	smartEN	Head of Research	SME	Belgium	https://smarten.eu
3	Black Sea Energy Research Centre	Manager, Chairman	Non-governmental organization	Bulgaria	www.bserc.eu
4	Green Synergy Cluster	Project Manager	Non-governmental organization	Bulgaria	https://greensynergycluster.eu
5	Airlux systems	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	www.airlux-v.com
6	Centre for Energy Efficiency EnEffect	Manager	Non-governmental organization	Bulgaria	www.eneffect.bg
7	Sofia Energy Centre	Senior Expert	SME	Bulgaria	https://sec.bg/en/

#	Organisation	Position	Type	Country	Website
8	Union of Bulgarian Black Sea Local Authorities (UBBSLA)	Project Coordinator	Non-governmental organization	Bulgaria	www.ubbsla.org/en
9	KEO-Zenit	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	https://keozenit.com
10	MJ Energy	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	-
11	PV Power	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	https://pvpower.bg
12	Eco-ST	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	-
13	ISE Energy	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	www.ise-industries.com/en/
14	Solery	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	https://baai-bg.org/en/solery-ltd
15	ABEA	Manager	Non-governmental organization	Bulgaria	https://new.abea-bg.org
16	Bulgarian-Austrian Consultancy Company	Manager	SME	Bulgaria	www.bacc-bg.org/en/
17	EcoEnergy	Manager	Non-governmental organization	Bulgaria	www.ecoenergy-bg.net
18	Kantor-Group	Consultant	Private for profit organisation	Greece	www.kantor-group.eu
19	COMMONEN energy community	Member of the board	Energy Community	Greece	www.commonen.gr/en/
20	ELECTRA ENERGY cooperative	Member of the board	Energy Community	Greece	https://electraenergy.coop/en/
21	Hypertech S.A.	Project Manager	SME	Greece	www.hypertech.gr
22	COLLECTIVE ENERGY	Member of the board	Energy Community	Greece	https://coen.coop/en/
23	Pragma-IoT	R&D Project Manager	SME	Greece	www.pragma-iot.com
24	METLEN Energy & Metals	EU Project Coordinator	Private for profit organisation	Greece	www.metlengroup.com
25	Innovatio	CEO	SME	Greece	www.innovatio.gr
26	ESB Networks	Flexibility Market Design Manager	Private for profit organisation	Ireland	https://esb.ie
27	GKinetic Energy Ltd	Chief Technical Officer	Private for profit organisation	Ireland	www.gkinetic.com
28	Atlantic Technical University (AI and Digital Excellence Research Cluster)	Lead of the AIDEX Cluster	Higher or secondary education establishment	Ireland	www.atu.ie

#	Organisation	Position	Type	Country	Website
29	Comharchumann Forbartha Árann	Chairperson and Manager	Energy Community	Ireland	www.cfarann.ie
30	Insight Research Ireland Centre for Data Analytics	Lead of the Applied Innovation Unit	Research Organisation	Ireland	www.insight-centre.org
31	Codema - Dublin's Energy Agency	Energy Systems Engineer	Research Organisation	Ireland	www.codema.ie
32	Enerit Ltd	Software Development Manager	SME	Ireland	https://enerit.com
33	MaREI Research Ireland Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine	Co Principal Investigator	Research Organisation	Ireland	www.marei.ie
34	EnGreen Srl	Head of Business Development	SME	Italy	https://engreen.world/en/
35	Aquavalor	Researcher	Research Organisation	Portugal	https://aquavalor.pt
36	Instituto Politecnico de Leiria	Researcher	Other	Portugal	www.ipleiria.pt
37	Kyndryl	Client Solutions Executive	Private for profit organisation	Portugal	www.kyndryl.com
38	Alba Iulia Municipality	Project Manager	Public organisation	Romania	www.apulum.ro
39	Institut Mihajlo Pupin	Director General	Research Organisation	Serbia	www.pupin.rs/en/
40	Instituto de Fomento de la Región de Murcia	Scientific park coordinator	Public organisation	Spain	www.institutofomento murcia.es
41	Asociación de Vecinos de Joven Futura	President	Non-governmental organization	Spain	www.jovenfutura.org
42	La Solar Cooperativa Energética	President	Other	Spain	www.lasolarenergiacoop.es
43	Comunidad Energética Local de Murcia	President	Non-governmental organization	Spain	www.celm.es
44	Centro Tecnológico de la Construcción Región de Murcia (CTCON)	Managing Director	Research Organisation	Spain	https://ctcon-rm.com/en/
45	Inspecciones Técnicas Albacete (DSO)	Partner	SME	Spain	-

#	Organisation	Position	Type	Country	Website
46	Electricidad Santa S.L.	Managing Director	SME	Spain	https://electricidadsanta.es
47	Centro Tecnológico del Mueble y la Madera (CETEM)	EU projects responsible	Research Organisation	Spain	https://cetem.es/en/
48	Municipality of Murcia	Head of European Programmes	Public organisation	Spain	https://web.murcia.es
49	Basque Energy Cluster	Project Engineer		Spain	www.clusterenergia.com
50	ALGINET DISTRIBUCIÓN ENERGÍA ELÉCTRICA, S.L.U.	Project Manager	Private for profit organisation	Spain	www.electricadealginet.com
51	APPA Renovables (Spanish Renewable Energy Association)	Director of projects	Non-governmental organization	Spain	www.appa.es
52	Comunidad CERES	President	Non-governmental organization	Spain	https://comunidadceres.es
53	CIRCE Foundation	CEO	Research Organisation	Spain	www.fcirce.es/en/
54	ENDEF Engineering SL	CEO	SME	Spain	https://endef.com
55	Solartys (Spanish cluster of solar energy companies)	Cluster manager	Non-governmental organization	Spain	www.solartys.org/en/
56	TRAZA Consultoría	Managing partner	SME	Spain	www.trazaconsultoria.com
57	Clúster de l'Energia Eficient de Catalunya CEEC	Cluster President	Private for profit organisation	Spain	www.clusterenergia.cat
58	Asociación Nacional de Empresas de Servicios Energéticos ANESE	Financing and Regulation Manager	Private for profit organisation	Spain	www.anese.es/en
59	Institut Català de l'Energia ICAEN	Energy management division	Public organisation	Spain	https://icaen.gencat.cat/
60	Deloitte Spain	Consulting - Business Operations	Private for profit organisation	Spain	www2.deloitte.com/es/
61	IREC - Institut de Recerca en Energia de Catalunya	Senior researcher	Research Organisation	Spain	www.irec.cat

#	Organisation	Position	Type	Country	Website
62	Ecoserveis	CEO	Research Organisation	Spain	https://ecoserveis.net/en/
63	Fundació Europace	Director	Research Organisation	Spain	www.fundacioeuropace.com
64	IVE - Instituto Valenciano de la Edificación	Architect and researcher	Research Organisation	Spain	www.five.es
65	LIMA - Low Impact Mediterranean Architecture	Industrial Engineer	Private for profit organisation	Spain	www.lima.cat
66	Luco Energía COOP	President	SME	Spain	www.energiacomun.org/comunidades/luco-energia
67	ESTRATS - Strategies for sustainability transitions	Industrial Engineer	Private for profit organisation	Spain	www.estrats.cat
68	CIMNE-UPC	Senior researcher	Research Organisation	Spain	www.cimne.com
69	Agencia Extremeña de la Energía AGENEX	Senior researcher	Public organisation	Spain	www.agenex.net/en/
70	BIIYUD, S.L. "Sustainability as Wealth"	CEO	SME	Spain	www.biyud.eco/en/
71	BAMBOO ENERGY PLATFORM, S.L.	President	SME	Spain	https://bambooenergy.tech/en/
72	Azienda Elettrica di Massagno (AEM) SA	Project Manager – Smart grids	Private for profit organisation	Switzerland	https://aemsa.ch
73	ENSİA Clean Energy Cluster	Chairman of the Board of Directors	Non-governmental organization	Turkey	www.ensia.org.tr
74	UFKABAKAN	Founder	SME	Turkey	https://ufkabakan.com.tr
75	No One Left Behind Sustainability Association	Co-Founder	Public organisation	Turkey	https://mlgp4climate.com/tr/mlgp-uyeleri/kimse-geride-kalmasin-surdurulebilirlik-dernegi
76	Ekobil Environmental Services and Consultancy Ltd.	Owner	Private for profit organisation	Turkey	www.ekobil.com
77	Glocal Group Inc.	Managing Director	Private for profit organisation	Turkey	https://groupglocal.com

#	Organisation	Position	Type	Country	Website
78	Green solar (Green Güneş Enerjisi Ür.Sis.San. ve Tic. Ltd.Şti.)	Co-Owner	Non-governmental organization	Turkey	https://greensolar.com.tr
79	Karabuk University	Assistant Professor	Research Organisation	Turkey	www.karabuk.edu.tr/en
80	Turkish Women in Renewables and Energy	Vice President	Public organisation	Turkey	https://twre.org
81	Green Collar Women Association (GCWA)	Founder & Chair	Non-governmental organization	Turkey	https://mlgp4climate.com/mlgp-members/green-collar-women-association
82	Impact Project House (IPH Teknoloji A.Ş)	Managing Director	Private for profit organisation	Turkey	https://impactprojecthouse.com
83	Çorum Renewable Energy Producing Cooperative	Chairman	Energy Community	Turkey	-
84	Güçyetmez Enerji	Manager	Private for profit organisation	Turkey	www.gucyetmez.com.tr
85	Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University - Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering	Head of Department	Research Organisation	Turkey	https://eem.muhendislik.comu.edu.tr
86	Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University - Department of Energy Management	Head of Department	Research Organisation	Turkey	https://global.comu.edu.tr
87	Troya Renewable Energy Cooperative	Chairman	Energy Community	Turkey	www.yenkoop.org
88	Izmir Energy Cooperative	Chairman	Energy Community	Turkey	-
89	Sakarya University of Applied Sciences	Professor - Department of Electricity and Energy	Higher or secondary education establishment	Turkey	www.subu.edu.tr/en
90	ANKA Smarthome Teknoloji	General Manager	SME	Turkey	www.ankasmarthome.com.tr
91	Bursa Teknik Üniversitesi - Electrical and Electronics Engineering Dept.	Associated Professor	Higher or secondary education establishment	Turkey	https://mdbf.btu.edu.tr/en/elektrik

#	Organisation	Position	Type	Country	Website
92	EnergyHUB	Project Supervisor	SME	Turkey	www.trenergyhub.com
93	ODTÜ-GÜNAM	Senior Researcher	Research Organisation	Turkey	https://odtugunam.org/tr/
94	HEFE Enerji Bilişim	Research And Development Engineer	SME	Turkey	https://hefe.com.tr
95	inavitas Enerji A.Ş.	R&D Lead	SME	Turkey	www.inavitas.com
96	International Power Electric Technology Company (IPET-CO)	Electrical Engineer	Private for profit organisation	Turkey	www.ipet-co.com
97	SEDAŞ	Business Development Officer	Private for profit organisation	Turkey	www.sedas.com/tr/
98	Seyyah Mühendislik	Electricity Network Manager	SME	Turkey	-
99	Niltek Yazılım Teknolojileri A.Ş	Business Development Director	Private for profit organisation	Turkey	www.niltekyazilim.com.tr
100	Saga Production and Consumption Cooperative	Chairman	Non-governmental organization	Turkey	-
101	LK Sustainability	Project Management Consultant	SME	United Kingdom	https://lukaszkuleszalin.k.wordpress.com/

The DE-RISK Market Actors Community has the following characteristics:

- **Figure 1** below shows that, overall, the stakeholder database has a good balance among the organisational types. Almost half of the DE-RISK stakeholders come from the industry or private enterprise sector (28.7% of SMES + 18.8% of larger for profit organisations). Also, the database has an important representation of research and academic institutions (20.8%). Lastly, there is a relevant representation of non-governmental organisations (15.8% of cluster associations, foundations, etc.), energy communities and cooperatives (6.9%), as well as public organisations (6.9%).

Figure 1: DE-RISK Market Actor Community clustered by type of organisation.

- **Figure 2** highlights the representation of 13 countries in the DE-RISK Market Actors Community, with a significant concentration of stakeholders in Spain (location to two of the four pilot sites), as well as in Turkey, Bulgaria, Greece and Ireland, where the majority of the Consortium partners are based.

Figure 2: DE-RISK Market Actor Community clustered by country.

3. CONCLUSIONS

This report has documented the approach for the DE-RISK Market Actors Community. The characteristics surrounding the targeted stakeholders are presented, and their analysis will be a tool for future decision-making related to the exploitation strategy.

The next step will be to use and leverage this database of key stakeholders' contacts. This will occur, practically, with the issue of the DE-RISK project's newsletters, the distribution of exploitation-oriented communication & dissemination materials, and the organisation of workshops in order to widely disseminate the DE-RISK project's activities and results and to gather feedback from key stakeholders and market actors.

The stakeholder database will keep growing along the project's lifetime. The milestone **MS13: +100 contacts in the DE-RISK Market Actors Community** has been achieved through the gathering of *Letters of Interest and Support* from key stakeholders across 13 countries.

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